

Association between obesity and musculoskeletal pain in preadolescent female students in Ha'il, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Objective and Method: The objective of the current study was to assess the relationship between obesity and the presence of musculoskeletal pain in spine, knee, and ankle on 571 preadolescent female students in Ha'il region, Saudi Arabia. Participants were recruited randomly from local primary schools. Children were classified as obese and non-obese based on body mass index (BMI) values. The association between obesity and pain areas (cervical, low back, knee, and ankle) was assessed. Body composition measures were also compared between obese and non-obese children with and without pain.

Results: The mean age of the total sample was 9.85 years and 162 (28.37%) students were categorized as obese. Concerning pain in a specific body area, the results indicated a significant relationship between obesity and cervical and knee pain. Obese children also had higher values in most body compositions and skinfold thickness measures compared to normal-weight children.

Conclusion: Primary school children with obesity are more likely to experience musculoskeletal pain in the cervical and knee areas compared to their normal-weight counterparts. The relationship between obesity and pain is complex and should be taken into consideration during the design of various rehabilitation techniques for obese children.

Keywords: Obesity, BMI, Musculoskeletal Pain, and Ha'il Region

Introduction

Obesity has been recognized as an epidemic problem in recent years due to the rapid spread of this problem among both children and adults and in both developed and developing countries (Roshdy et al. 2020). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), obesity affects more than a third of the world population (WHO 2017; Wyatt et al. 2006). In Saudi Arabia, it has been found that 30-70% of the population is obese where this percentage varies according to region, race, sex, and age (Hussein et al. 2021; Khan 2014). Similarly, high prevalence rates of obesity have been reported among children and preadolescents (Mahmood & Arulkumaran 2012). The prevalence of obesity in the Ha'il region is the highest among the different regions of Saudi Arabia, especially among females where obesity represents 63.3% (Ahmed et al. 2014).

The risk of morbidity and mortality increases with obesity, due to dyslipidemia, insulin resistance, gastrointestinal diseases, sleep disorders, cardiovascular insults, cancer, infertility, a decline in mobility (El Kasem et al. 2020), and musculoskeletal pain (Adams et al. 2014; Seiluri et al. 2011). Musculoskeletal problems are considered common health conditions among older and children age groups (Picavet & Schouten 2003). Musculoskeletal problems have significant effects on health status, disability level, self-esteem, and physical performance (Ferguson et al. 2013; Murray et al. 2012). Obesity is recognized as a modifiable risk factor for musculoskeletal system disorders such as low back pain, knee, and foot pain (Hussein et al. 2019).

The management strategies of musculoskeletal pain should consider the definition of the cause and the nature of risk factors associated with obesity, and therefore many recent

studies have been conducted to understand the relation between obesity and musculoskeletal pain. The overall findings demonstrated that individuals with overweight and obesity reported more non-specific region-specific musculoskeletal pain compared to their normal-weight counterparts. Low back, knees, and feet are the most common sites that exhibit pain in obese persons. Brady et al. stated that low back pain represents 63% of the total cases, as well as pain in two sites, represents 26.3% of the subjects and 31.6% for three sites, while 20% were free from pain. The study was conducted on adults and both genders were included but the females represent most of the cases (78.2%) (Brady et al. 2015).

Compared to adults, studies conducted on children in relation to the development and progression of musculoskeletal pain in children with obesity are scarce. Despite the limited number of studies, the findings revealed that obese children are more likely to have musculoskeletal pain than those of normal weight (Stovitz et al. 2008). Concerning the area-specific musculoskeletal pain, low back, knee, ankle, and foot pain were the most commonly reported sites of pain (Bell et al. 2011; Hainsworth et al. 2009; Taylor et al. 2006).

The majority of previous studies relating musculoskeletal pain and obesity focused on body mass measures such as body mass index (BMI). The findings of these studies demonstrate the need for investigating the relation of body segments and fat distribution with different sites of musculoskeletal pain (Berry et al. 2010; Brady et al. 2015). Some studies have investigated the relationship between the fat mass and specific sites of pain (e.g., foot) found that there is a positive correlation between fat mass and incident of foot pain; for example (Butterworth et al. 2013; Urquhart et al. 2011). Other studies that were conducted to assess the relationship between body fat mass, the structure of the foot and its function

found a strong association between these variables as obese participants tend to have a low arched foot (flat foot) and increase the loading on the plantar aspect which increase the risk of foot pain (Butterworth et al. 2015). Despite the link between some body composition measures and specific-body region among adults, the relationship has not been explored in musculoskeletal pain profile (cervical, lumbar, knee, ankle, and foot) among children with obesity.

The association between obesity and pain is complex and can be caused by several factors including genetic, environmental factors, diet, and lifestyle. From a biomechanical view, obesity places an excessive load on the joints which increases the stress and ground reaction force inside these joints. Additionally, there is a positive correlation between obesity and inflammatory biomarkers. Particularly, obesity results in an increase in the secretion of proinflammatory biomarkers from adipose tissues, and this can lead to systemic inflammation; therefore, it is assumed that obesity and inflammation increase associated-pathophysiological changes which in turn worsen inflammatory processes in a vicious cycle leading to the emergence of musculoskeletal pain (Ellulu et al. 2017; Rodriguez-Hernandez et al. 2013). Musculoskeletal pain, according to the psychosocial models, can also be extended and elicited even if there are no definite soft tissue insults that can be affected by pain perception, psychological mood, and physical inactivity (Petrus et al. 2020; Sullivan et al. 2015).

There is a lack of studies that investigate the association of obesity with musculoskeletal pain during the childhood period, especially in Saudi Arabia. The heterogeneity of the samples recruited in the previous studies and the wide range of age may complicate the

interpretation and generalizability of these findings. Moreover, another limitation encountered in previous studies is the neglect of other important measures for obesity and overweight. The majority of these studies used Body Mass Index (BMI) as the main measure of obesity and overweight. However, BMI cannot distinguish fat from lean body mass and cannot represent the regional body distribution of fat. Thus, the current study was conducted to investigate the association between obesity and the presence of musculoskeletal pain in spine, knee, and ankle of preadolescent females in Ha'il city, Saudi Arabia, and the effect of body composition measurements with these pain areas.

Materials & Methods

Sitting and Subjects:

A cross-sectional observational study was conducted between January to March 2020. The study was conducted on the preparatory schools in Ha'il Region, Saudi Arabia, where 4 schools were randomly selected from a list of all schools. The gender of the participants was female where 571 students included in this study with ages ranged from 6-12 years. Additionally, BMI was used to classify the students into obese ($BMI \geq 25$), and non-obese ($BMI < 25$) (Aljabri & Bokhari 2014). The study was reviewed and approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the University of Ha'il, Saudi Arabia (Protocol #: H-2020-160).

Instruments and procedures

The recruitment of participants in the current study targeted female students in primary schools in which an email was distributed to all the primary schools located within Ha'il Region, Northern of Saudi Arabia. This email contained the objectives of the study

and the data needed to be collected as well as an invitation to who was willing to participate in the study. Seven schools agreed to participate in the study. The name of the seven schools was written and everyone was inserted in a separate envelope, then the author asked a person who was blinded by the study to select four envelopes randomly. Before the commencement of the study, all subjects were informed about the purpose and the content of the study, and informed consent was signed by the students' parents. Participants were excluded if they have any specific medical condition such as spinal or other deformities, cardiac, respiratory diseases, and the students who reached puberty as it can affect the anthropometric measures as well as associated physical pain.

Each participant was assigned a code number for the datasheet through a research assistant. A research assistant collected personal information (nationality, age, and grades) and asked about the presence of musculoskeletal pain in the cervical, lumbar, knee, and ankle. Also, all the anthropometric measurements were conducted such as stretching height, weight, diameters, and skinfold thickness (SF).

Outcome measurements:

Weight, height, and Body Mass Index:

Weight was measured using a digital measuring device. Height was measured using a large paper ruler that was fixed to a wall. The student was asked to be barefoot and stand with his back facing the paper ruler. the student was asked to stand erect to record the stretching standing height (Al-Agha et al. 2016). The advantage of this way of measurement is to preserve the height throughout the day (Riolo et al. 2005). BMI was calculated by dividing the weight (kg) by the squared height (m²) (Hussien et al. 2017). According to the

BMI measurements, students were classified as obese if their BMI ≥ 25 and non-obese if BMI < 25 .

Girth and diameter and waist-hip ratio:

Waist and hip girth were measured by flexible rubber measuring tape in cm. Students assumed standing position, waist circumference was measured at the level of the midway between the last rib and iliac crest. The hip girth was measured at the level of the widest area of the hip region (Marfell-Jones et al. 2012). The waist-hip ratio was also calculated by dividing the values of the waist and hip girth (Marfell-Jones et al. 2012).

Skinfold thickness:

Seven standard locations were measured; triceps, biceps, subscapular, supraspinale, abdominal, calf and front thigh points were assessed. The methods of the measurements were adopted according to the international standards for anthropometric assessment (Marfell-Jones et al. 2012). A plastic-made 6-cm skin fold caliper was used and the values were recorded in mm.

Musculoskeletal pain:

Students were asked about their chronic experience of pain in different areas of the body. Five areas were screened for the presence of chronic pain: cervical, lumbar, knee, and ankle. The pain was considered chronic if it lasts more than 3 months (Treede et al. 2019).

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were carried out using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 23.0. All data were expressed as mean \pm SD and the normality of

the collected data was examined using Shapiro-Wilk test. Additionally, Chi-square was used to examine the relationship between the categorical variables. t-test was used to estimate the effect of obesity on the presence of musculoskeletal pain with Levene's test due to unequal sample numbers. The differences were considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results

A descriptive analysis was conducted on 571 female students as illustrated in Table 1. The frequency of the areas of pain among the total sample was presented in Figure 1. In general, 83 female students reported experiencing pain in several areas of the body with a prevalence of 16%. Regarding specific body areas, pain in the cervical, lumbar, and knee areas was reported by 3.9, 3, and 3.9% of students, respectively. Pain in the ankle area was reported only by 0.9% of students. The students were categorized into non-obese and obese groups based on the findings of BMI. 162 students (28.37%) were classified as obese whereas 409 (71.63%) were in the non-obese category.

A chi-square test of independence was performed to examine the relationship between BMI and pain in the abovementioned areas. There was a significant association between the BMI and the cervical and knee pain (Table 2); suggesting that obese students were more likely than non-obese to experience pain in cervical and knee areas [Cervical area: $X^2(1, N = 517) = 26.926, P < 0.05$; Knee area: $X^2(1, N = 517) = 7.714, P = 0.008$]. In contrast, there was no significant correlation between BMI and pain in the lumbar and ankle areas (Table 2).

Table 1: The demographic data of the participants (Mean \pm SD)

	Non-obese (n=409) 71.63% Mean \pm SD	Obese (n=162) 28.37% Mean \pm SD
Age (year)	8.61 \pm 1.81	9.97 \pm 1.65
Weight (kg)	26.79 \pm 6.53	46.34 \pm 12.17
Height (cm)	125.88 \pm 11.85	136 \pm 12.69
BMI Z score (w/m²)	19.56 \pm 2.51	29.33 \pm 4.49
Waist-hip ratio	1.02 \pm 0.84	0.94 \pm 0.31
Waist girth (cm)	64.02 \pm 9.07	78.51 \pm 8.24
Arm girth (cm)	22.36 \pm 2.5	27.77 \pm 3.52
Hip girth (cm)	68.46 \pm 11.35	88.66 \pm 23.84
Midhigh girth (cm)	33.39 \pm 3.8	42.35 \pm 4.86
SFof biceps (mm)	4.47 \pm 3.12	5.07 \pm 2.33
SFof triceps (mm)	4.94 \pm 2.34	7.16 \pm 2.4
SFof subscapular (mm)	3.91 \pm 1.81	5.56 \pm 2.5
SFof abdominal (mm)	5.98 \pm 3.3	9.33 \pm 3.15
SFof iliac crest (mm)	4.15 \pm 2.29	6.74 \pm 3.22
SFof supraspinal (mm)	4.14 \pm 2.16	6.97 \pm 2.5
SFof ant. Thigh (mm)	5.81 \pm 3.14	8.38 \pm 3.57

n, number; SD, standard deviation; kg, kilogram; cm, centimeter; SF, skinfold thickness; mm, millimeter

Table 2: The association between body mass index (BMI) and musculoskeletal pain sites

	BMI		
	χ^2	Df	P-Value
Cervical	26.926	1	0.000*
Lumbar	0.413	1	0.586
Knee	7.714	1	0.008*
Ankle	1.998	1	0.329

* significant as $P \leq 0.05$

The majority of body composition measures (waist girth, SF of triceps, and SF of abdominal) were significantly higher in students with cervical pain. The SF in the triceps areas was significantly higher in students showing lumbar pain. The mean of the SF was higher in the obese group. The mean of waist girth and triceps SF was significantly higher in students with knee pain. On the other hand, the mean of the waist girth was significantly higher in students with ankle pain (Table 3).

Table 3: The effect of body composition measurements on the areas of pain sites

	Cervical		Lumbar		Knee		Ankle	
	No Pain (n=549) M ± SD	Pain (n=22) M ± SD	No Pain (n=554) M ± SD	Pain (n=17) M ± SD	No Pain (n=549) M ± SD	Pain (n=22) M ± SD	No Pain (n=566) M ± SD	Pain (n=5) M ± SD
Waist-hip ratio	0.99±0.73	1.29±0.69	1±0.74	0.93±0.5	1±1.74	1.07±0.26	1±1.54	1.54±0.00
P-value	0.57		0.69		0.626		0.096	
hip girth (cm)	74.44±18.07	68.14±24.13	73.96±18.15	81.82±23.21	74.3±18.63	71.45±8.24	74.27±18.41	65±0.00
P-value	0.239		0.185		0.476		0.261	
SF of triceps (mm)	5.52±2.6	6.77±0.87	5.47±2.5	8.82±2.56	5.47±2.47	8.23±3.34	5.59±2.57	4±0.00
P-value	0.000*		0.000*		0.000*		0.000*	
SF of abdominal (mm)	6.84±3.6	9.09±2.29	6.96±3.63	6±1.73	6.88±3.6	8.27±3.22	6.96±3.6	4±0.00
P-value	0.004*		0.044*		0.074		0.000*	
SF of ant. Thigh (mm)	6.56±3.49	6.18±2.89	6.64±3.47	3.47±1.7	6.47±3.07	8.32±8.79	6.59±3.45	1±0.00
P-value	0.621		0.000*		0.336		0.000*	

* significant as $P \leq 0.05$

n, number; SD, standard deviation; kg, kilogram; cm, centimeter; SF, skinfold thickness; mm, millimeter

Discussion

Obesity has gained a considerable amount of attention in recent years. This attention has been increased due to the rapid increment in prevalence of obesity and overweight among both pediatric and adult populations and in both developed and developing countries (Wyatt et al. 2006). In regard to musculoskeletal pain and obesity as categorized based on BMI values, the findings of the current study showed a significant association between BMI and cervical and knee pain. To the best of our knowledge, studies investigating the relationship between obesity and musculoskeletal pain are scarce in literature especially among children and adolescent populations.

According to most previous studies, obesity is recognized as a significant risk factor for non-specific and area-specific musculoskeletal pain. Our findings are consistent with previous studies in that it demonstrates more musculoskeletal pain among children with obesity compared to normal-weight children. Specifically, our findings showed that children with obesity reported more musculoskeletal pain in cervical and knee areas. In contrast to most previous studies, we did not find a significant difference in lumbar and ankle areas among our participants when BMI was used to determine obesity.

Some previous studies reported that children with obesity have higher odds of experiencing non-specific musculoskeletal pain compared to normal-weight children (Bell et al. 2011; Hainsworth et al. 2009). Concerning area-specific musculoskeletal pain, the areas in which pain was reported in previous studies on schoolchildren with obesity were somewhat variable. Adams et al, demonstrated that children (age range=2–19 years) had significantly higher odds of lower extremity injuries/pain compared to normal-weight

children, and such difference was not found for pain in the upper extremity (Adams et al. 2013).

Stovitz et al. (2008) reported that 61% of children and adolescent (mean age=12.3 years) complained of pain in at least one area of the body more than once per month with back pain was the most common complaint (39%), followed by foot (26%), and knee (24%) pain. Taylor et al conducted a medical chart review study to compare musculoskeletal pain among obese and non-obese children (mean age of obese children= 12.6 years). The latter study concluded that obese children experience more musculoskeletal pain in multiple areas including back, hip, leg, knee, ankle, and foot pain; with the knee area was the most affected area (6.6%) compared to other body areas (Taylor et al. 2006). Bell and colleagues found that primary school children (mean age = 9.8 years) reported significantly more musculoskeletal pain compared to normal-weight children; with the most common site was the knees; however, the occurrence of pain in other body areas was not reported in the study (Bell et al. 2011).

Our findings were consistent with few studies that demonstrated an association between obesity and neck pain among children. Azabagic & Pranjic (2019) investigated the primary school children aged 9-14 years in Bosnia and Herzegovina. They stated that the most common places for chronic pain associated with overweight and obesity were the neck (OR = 1.212, 95% CI, 0.893-1.644) and the knee (OR = 1.103, 95% CI, 0.690- 1.760). While the most commonplace of acute pain was knee (OR = 1.127, 95% CI, 0.673-1.890). Krul et al. (2009) found that children in the age range 2-11 years experienced more musculoskeletal problems compared to normal-weight children (5.1% neck and back pain; 6.8% lower

extremity pain; 1.7% hip and knee pain; 5.11% ankle and foot pain). In contrast, there was no significant difference between obese and non-obese children in the experience of pain in the upper extremity area.

From a biomechanical perspective, excessive weight and obesity likely result in an excess load on the musculoskeletal system which consequently leads to the onset and development of musculoskeletal pain. Obesity has the greatest effect on the knee alignment compared to other joints of the lower extremities. It has been proposed that the increase of the axial loading will increase the demand on the endochondral ossification of the epiphysis and extreme changes in the angulation of the knee due to varus malalignment causing deviation during amputation resulting in compressive forces on the medial side of the knee joint. The joint reaction force is multiplied by three to five times the body weight during various activities such as walking, jogging, and climbing stairs; therefore, the loading on the joints will be more tremendous in obese children than the normal weight, this hypothesis was noticed during our analysis as there was significant effect between low back pain and the SF of triceps (Wearing et al. 2006). Another explanation was reported by de Sá Pinto et al, obese individuals have tightness of the quadriceps muscle more than non-obese individuals. This may be reflected in the mechanics of the body causing the increase of anterior pelvic tilt adding more compressive force on the lumbar area causing pain (de Sá Pinto et al. 2006).

BMI is considered the most commonly used measure for assessing obesity and overweight among children and adolescents 2 to 19 years of age (Krebs & Jacobson 2003). However, BMI poses some disadvantages in quantifying the body composition and

differentiating between lean mass and fat body mass among children and adolescents. It has been suggested that anthropometric measurements, such as skinfold thickness, segment girths, and waist circumference provide a more accurate assessment of the regional distribution of body fat than BMI (Krebs et al. 2007).

As noticed in the current study, waist girth was significantly higher in students with ankle pain. The ankle joint is highly vulnerable to stress in obese children as it receives the weight of the whole body above it. The increase in peripheral or central obesity places an excessive load on the ankle joint and may contribute to the onset and progression of pain. The increase in the joint reaction force might be a reasonable cause for the development of ankle pain (Wearing et al. 2006). In light of the findings of the current study, the cervical, and lumbar, knee, and ankle pain were higher among obese children. Consequently, health care professionals dealing with obesity management in children should consider screening and treatment of musculoskeletal pain that might be present in this population.

This study had few limitations inherent in the design of the study. Being descriptive, caution should be considered when interpreting these results. Although we used self-reported measures to assess for pain, we believe the format of the face-to-face interview could provide some degree of validity to the answers provided by students. The relatively low sample size could be another limitation that suggests that further studies including a larger number of children are required. This study was included only female children suggesting that future studies should consider both genders.

Conclusions

Central and peripheral obesity should be considered as indicators as well as BMI during assessment of the effect of the obesity in primary school children. Musculoskeletal pain is more common in obese school-age female children compared to normal-weight children; particularly in cervical and knee areas. In the light of the complexity of obesity and pain as comorbidity factors, the relation between them should be taken in consideration during the establishment of various rehabilitation techniques for obese children.

Conflict of interest:

The authors declared no conflicts of interest regarding the authorship and/or publication of this article.

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